

Control of tungro (RTV) and yellow stem borer (YSB) in rice by synthetic pyrethroids

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Resurgence of insect pests following repeated insecticide applications has become widespread. We evaluated foliar application of available synthetic pyrethroids in controlling RTV vector green leafhoppers (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) and *N. nigropictus* Stål and YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* Walker.

Two field experiments were conducted in wet season (Jul-Nov) 1984 using rice variety Ratna, which is tolerant of both RTV and YSB. Thirty-d-old seedlings were transplanted in 3- × 3-m plots at 20- × 15-cm spacing (300 hills) late in the season (12 Sep) to synchronize the RTV-vulnerable, early tillering stage with emergence of GLH in mid-Sep to mid-Oct and the flowering stage YSB (end of Oct to mid-Nov). The crop was grown with 100-18-33 kg NPK/ha. Five days after transplanting (DT), 2 m around each plot was transplanted with RTV inoculated seedlings in the glasshouse.

In the first experiment, decamethrin

and cypermethrin were sprayed six times. In the second experiment, synthetic pyrethroids decamethrin + bufrofezin, tralomethrin, S.399, and S.423. decamethrin and cypermethrin were sprayed four times. Adult and nymph populations were monitored at 30 and 42 DT and RTV disease at 49-51 DT. Stem borer infestation at heading (% whiteheads) was estimated from 4 random samples of 20 hills each.

Treatments differed significantly (see table). In both experiments, synthetic pyrethroids gave good to excellent control of both RTV and its vector, but were not effective against YSB. □

Control of RTV, GLH, and YSB by some synthetic pyrethroids.^a Cuttack, India, 1984 kharif.

Insecticide	Dose (ai/ha)	Green leafhopper/10 hills				Disease (%) (49-51 d)	YSB infestation at heading	
		Adult		Nymph			Whiteheads (%)	Angular value
		30 DT	42 DT	30 DT	42 DT			
A. Decamethrin	200 g	0.3 a	3.0 ab	0.3 a	nil a	1.7 a	3.9	11.34 ab
	100 g	1.3 ab	3.7 ab	1.3 ab	0.3 a	1.9 a	12.0	20.21 cdef
	50 g	0.7 a	4.0 b	3.0 b	nil a	3.7 b	14.6	22.36 ef
	25 g	0.3 bc	5.0 b	3.7 b	0.7 ab	4.5 bc	13.9	21.90 def
	12 g	2.7 bc	5.0 b	3.0 b	1.0 ab	4.7 bc	11.6	19.87 cde
	6 g	6.7 d	9.7 c	10.3 c	3.0 b	5.2 bc	8.6	16.97 cd
	2 g	1.3 ab	1.7 a	2.0 ab	nil a	2.1 a	15.6	23.02 ef
Cypermethrin	100 g	1.3 ab	1.7 a	2.0 ab	nil a	2.1 a	15.6	23.02 ef
Carbofuran (treated check)	2 kg	4.3 cd	5.0 b	20.3 d	2.0 ab	11.6 d	1.6	6.82 a
Control (untreated check)	-	16.0 e	34.7 d	98.3 e	53.3 c	43.6 e	7.7	15.80 bc
B. Synthetic pyrethroids								
Decamethrin + bufrofezin	100 g	11.7 bcde	8.0 ab	4.3 ab	3.0 abc	8.4 bc	10.6	18.79 cd
	200 g	8.7 abcd	6.0 a	2.3 a	1.3 a	5.9 ab	8.2	16.40 bcd
Tralomethrin	10 g	6.3 ab	9.7 ab	6.7 b	5.0 bc	9.5 c	9.5	17.90 cd
	20 g	5.0 ab	8.3 ab	2.3 a	1.0 a	4.1 a	11.0	19.27 cd
S. 399	125 g	30.0 g	18.0 cd	41.0 a	15.3 d	38.9 f	7.2	15.47 bc
	250 g	18.7 efg	14.0 ab	27.0 d	12.3 d	23.8 e	8.0	16.36 bcd
S. 423	500 g	20.0 fg	6.3 a	13.0 c	5.0 c	14.5 d	7.1	15.43 bc
	1000 g	15.7 def	12.7 bc	6.3 ab	2.0 a	8.3 bc	8.4	16.68 bcd
Decamethrin	12 g	6.3 abc	8.3 ab	3.3 ab	1.0 a	5.2 ab	8.0	16.46 bcd
Cypermethrin	50 g	2.7 a	7.0 ab	3.0 ab	1.7 a	4.6 a	12.6	20.54 d
Carbofuran (treated check)	2 kg	13.7 cdef	9.0 ab	13.7 c	2.3 ab	10.6 cd	0.03	6.03 a
Control (untreated check)	-	29.3 g	21.0 d	59.0 f	37.3 e	42.3 f	4.9	12.75 b

^aWithin a group, means in a column followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Rice thrips infestations in West Bengal

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Rice thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) is essentially a pest of young rice plants. On wetland or monsoon

season rice (kharif), maximum infestation is found Jul-Aug when rice is in nursery beds or at tillering in the field. However, a severe outbreak occurred at late tillering in West Bengal in Sep 1986. An estimated 60,000 ha was affected. A prolonged dry spell from Aug to the third week of Sep in the middle of the rainy season may have been one of the causes.

Another thrips species, *Haplothrips gunglbaueri* Schmutz, commonly known as rice ear thrips, damages the inflorescence of early varieties. It is polyphagous and has been recorded on other crops. On rice, adults and nymphs congregate on the emerging inflorescence, lacerate the lemma and palea of the spikelet, and suck the content. Symptoms include ear